

5

Pedagogical Issues and Practices of Social Work Education

Prashant S. Bhosale
PhD Scholar, NMU,
Jalgaon, Jalgaon (MS) India

Dr. Jagadish Jadhav
PhD Research Guide,
NMU, Jalgaon, Dist. Jalgaon (MS) India

Research Paper - Social Work

ABSTRACT

The participatory approach of social work education is about the skills, techniques and knowledge of people participation for social development. The teachers are academically engage with the pedagogical practices in class rooms. This paper is an endeavor to study academic engagement of teachers to improve skills, attitude and knowledge among students about Social Work Education in context of North Maharashtra Region.

Introduction:

The pedagogical practices of social work education (SWE) across the country are different. The changing social political and cultural realities enforce policy reforms in higher education. Hence it is essential to study teaching methods and learning outcomes of SWE. This research paper is an attempt to discuss issues of pedagogical practices and students experiences in North Maharashtra region.

Objective:

To explore the innovative teaching-learning models of SWE and practices

Hypothesis:

The academic engagement of a teacher is directly proportionate to qualitative improvement of Social Work Students and education.

Methodology:

The all social work colleges affiliated to North Maharashtra University will be the universe of study. It covers three districts i.e. Jalgaon, Dhule and Nadurbar. These districts have six social work institutions including a department of Social Work at university campus. Bhagini Mandal's Social Work College, Chopda, Jalgaon; Dhanaji Nana Choudhary Vidya Prabodhini's Social work College, Kusumba, Jalgaon; Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru Social Work College, Amlner, Jalgaon; Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar College of Social Work Education, Morane, Dhule and Mahatma Phule College of Social Work, Taloda, Nadurbar the aforesaid enlisted colleges and Social Work Department of NMU, Jalgaon were the locus of study.

This research study was a combination of qualitative and quantitative investigation. The descriptive cum exploratory research design was adopted for the study. Primary and secondary method of data collection was used. The SPSS is a computerized tool of data analysis used for analysis. The method of sampling was simple random sampling, under that sequential and quota sampling method was adopted. This research paper is based on the sample size of 304 students out of total sample size of 492.

Total Sample size was including 25 student Alumni, 25 students of final year, 25 students of first year, 5 teachers and 2 management personnel i.e. 82 sample from each social work institution. The total sample size was 492 including 25 student alumni of social work department of university campus.

Pedagogical issues in SWE:

The different colleges have different specialization in social work courses whereas few universities follow generic courses. The numbers of theory papers also have no standardization in its occurrence. The unorganized and irrelevant pedagogy in field practice brings poor learning opportunities for learners. Most of the academic institutions have no student centric infrastructures. Systemic inculcation of social work values and knowledge of legacy and ethos in students and teachers are essential to arrive at stage of

self-actualization. The medium of instructions in SWE has also disparity. Most of the state universities having English as a medium of instruction, whereas bio-lingual medium of instructions are essential need of students for understanding the crux of SWE. Ironically SWE is vividly dominated by western literature, which limits the access of students to indigenous knowledge. The western outlook of social work education has its own limitation in the Indian context. Indigenous practice wisdom in working with communities and groups are needed to design SWE for attaining goal of social justice. Field action projects at every university and colleges should set as learning workstation of social change for student and teachers. Ethnographic research and monographs are significant tools to know field of realities and needs of communities. Students should engage in research activities to have scientific study and analysis of the particular field areas. It will bring practical insights from theory and models of SWE to direct social change.

In the scenario of fast changing world, social worker should equipped themselves with updated knowledge, skills and attitude to practice in an innovative way to deal with social problems. The skill laboratories and regular workshops are essential in respect to this but ignored in most of the colleges. Skill based education is inevitable as students are trained to deal with human relations and their environment. In the assurance of quality education, faculty- student ratio is important indicator to impart knowledge through interactive sessions. In early beginning of SWE faculty-student ratio was 1:8, which goes up to 1:14. The unfavorable teacher-student ratio and increased teaching load is the immediate cause in qualitative dwindle of SWE.

Pedagogical Practices of SWE in North Maharashtra Region:

Social Work Education is relevant stream in the contemporary social context of Indian society. The students of social work education are aspirant to do social development. Today the era is of liberalization, privatization and globalization (LPG). The policy of higher education has impacts of LPG. Hence proliferation of private colleges and universities are coming across the nation. The no. of autonomous colleges and deemed universities are increasing. Hence academic social work institutions are come up under the standardization norms of higher education.

University of Grants Commission has measuring scale for quality assessment of

social work institutions. India is excelling in academics, research and extension activities. The quality higher education is possible by ensuring the accountability in public domain with periodic assessment and accreditation of Universities and colleges. In the milieu of India, quality higher education is about relevance and excellence of academic programmes. Under the flagship of NAAC quality measurement of higher education have designed seven criteria i.e. Curricular Aspects, Teaching-Learning and Evaluation, Research, Consultancy and Extension, Infrastructure and Learning Resources, Student Support and Progression, Governance and Leadership and Innovative Practices. These seven indicators can help us to explore quality concern of SWE.

The below table: 1 is the study of teaching methods across all affiliated social work colleges of NMU, Jalgaon with the learning output. It primarily focused on skills

Teaching Methods	Learning Output			Total
	Singing or Street play or drama	Skills, techniques and knowledge to get people participation	Attitude of social welfare	
Reading Books	6	62	30	98
<i>Cumulative Presentation</i>	<i>100.0%</i>	<i>27.6%</i>	<i>41.1%</i>	<i>32.2%</i>
Power Point Presentations	0	61	12	73
<i>Cumulative Presentation</i>	<i>.0%</i>	<i>27.1%</i>	<i>16.4%</i>	<i>24.0%</i>
Dictation of Notes	0	48	7	55
<i>Cumulative Presentation</i>	<i>.0%</i>	<i>21.3%</i>	<i>9.6%</i>	<i>18.1%</i>
Conceptual Maps and Presentations	0	54	24	78
<i>Cumulative Presentation</i>	<i>.0%</i>	<i>24.0%</i>	<i>32.9%</i>	<i>25.7%</i>
Total	6	225	73	304
<i>Cumulative Presentation</i>	<i>100.0%</i>	<i>100.0%</i>	<i>100.0%</i>	<i>100.0%</i>

$$X = 24.510 \quad df = 6 \quad n = 304 \quad P < 0.05$$

The teachers of social work education are using teaching methods broadly as mentioned in table : 1 Reading books, Conceptual Maps-Presentations, Power Point Presentations and Dictation of Notes. As per the 32.3 % of total student respondents

narrated their experiences that teachers are using books in class room teaching as reading book and explanations. The technological use by teachers is also increased where 25.7% and 24 % students have responded to increase use of conceptual maps and power point presentations for class room teaching respectively. The Skills, techniques and knowledge to get people participation are developed in all students due to various teaching methods are observed. The 'reading book' and 'conceptual map-presentations' methods helped mostly to bring good learning outputs for 54.7 %. It is followed by development of student's social welfare attitude where 41.1 % student respondents were developed due to 'reading book' as a teaching method.

The chi square table value is 24.510 where degree of freedom is 6 and significant p value is less than 0.05. Hence there is significant relationship between teaching methods and qualitative learning outcomes such as Skills, techniques and knowledge to get people participation. It enhances the participatory approach among student social workers to social development. Hence it proved the hypothesis that academic engagement of a teacher is directly proportionate to qualitative improvement of Social Work Students and education. Still continuous efforts are needed to do standardization in SWE teaching and practice.

Expectations of standardization in SWE:

'Social Work Literature' is a literature specific to social work profession. SWE should transcend Social Work Literature. It could be achieved with linking of past with present context of social realities and theories. The inclusion of indigenous practice wisdom with theoretical analysis of social problems will bring indigenous way of thinking towards issues of human relations and environment. SWE should be analyzed in reference with importance to scienticism and post modernism. 'Social work practice is an ever changing and complex blend of theory, analogue, wisdom and art' (Desai M. 1996). Recognition of realities is related with cognitive resources. Indigenous thoughts and practice wisdom could create Indigenous theory of SWE in India. So documentation or publications of such indigenous practice models are significant tool in knowledge creation, sharing and communication of social realities.

References

1. Desai M., Jaswal S., Sudha G Ed. (2000), Social Work Knowledge, Development and Dissemination, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai.
2. Lawni B.T., Jadhav Jagdish (2010), Governance of Social Work Education in Maharashtra: In Search of Space For Quality, University News, 48 (45) November 08-14,2010, page 128-132
3. Manshardt Clifford (1940), Education and Social Change, Opening Assembly Address The Sir Dorabji Tata Graduate School of Social Work for the year 1940, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai.
4. Menachery J., Mohite A. (2001), Whither Social Work Education in Maharashtra, Indian Journal of Social Work, volume 62(1), January, 106-122.
5. Siddique H. (1987), Towards a Competency Based Education for Social Work, Indian Journal of Social Work, 48(1), 23-32.
6. UGC (2001) Model Curriculum, 2001, Social Worker Education, University Grants Commission, New Delhi.